

EVALUATION OF INTERFACIAL AND FIBER PROPERTIES IN TITANIUM MATRIX COMPOSITES BY SINGLE FIBER FRAGMENTATION TESTING

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ABSTRACT

Single fiber fragmentation tests were performed on SiC fiber reinforced titanium matrix composites to evaluate interfacial shear properties and *in-situ* fiber strengths. Testing was performed on a range of samples incorporating different matrices, fibers, fiber surface coatings, and processing conditions. Data were acquired by acoustic emission and scanning electron and confocal microscopy of fibers exposed by electropolishing. Fractography of fiber failures was performed. Fibers investigated included Textron SCS-0, SCS-6, and Ultra SCS and Sigma single and triplex carbon coated fibers. Matrices included Ti-22Al-23Nb (at.%) containing the "O" phase and the conventional Ti-6Al-4V (wt.%) alloy for comparison.

INTRODUCTION

Presently there is considerable interest in fiber reinforced titanium aluminide composites based on Ti₃Al alloys with high levels (>15 at.%) of Nb, which contain significant amounts of the ordered orthorhombic (O) Ti₂AlNb phase [1]. This interest stems from the results of recent studies [2] which showed that SiC fiber reinforced titanium aluminide matrix composites containing a high volume fraction of the "O" phase exhibit high tensile strengths at room and elevated temperatures, improved ductility, thermal stability, superior creep resistance, and increased resistance to both thermal fatigue and thermo-mechanical fatigue as compared to previously developed titanium composites based on ($\alpha_2 + \beta$), β or ($\alpha + \beta$) phases. To date, much of this activity has focused on development of composites with improved matrix alloys. There is clearly a need for understanding the fiber-matrix interfacial behavior in these new composite systems. The present work is a part of a larger research effort which was undertaken to address this need.

EXPERIMENTAL

Two different titanium alloys, Ti-6Al-4V (wt.%) and Ti-22Al-23Nb (at.%), were used as matrix material in these composites. The fibers used were (1) uncoated SiC SCS-0, (2) SCS-6 with two carbon + SiC coating layers, (3) Ultra SCS high strength SiC fiber with carbon + SiC coating layers, (4) A3C triplex three layer "soft" carbon coated tungsten core fiber and (5) A1C single hard carbon coated tungsten core fiber. The selection of the two matrices was based on the following considerations. The most common ($\alpha + \beta$) titanium alloy, Ti-6Al-4V, was used as a baseline for comparison. The Ti-22Al-23Nb alloy, containing a significant amount of the orthorhombic phase, has shown several advantages over other titanium aluminide alloys based on the alpha-2 phase such as Ti-24Al-11Nb. These advantages include reduced fiber/matrix reaction, high specific strength, and higher resistance to interstitial embrittlement [3]. Hot pressing of the microcomposites based on Ti-6Al-4V and Ti-22Al-23Nb matrices was carried out at 925 C° and 1010 C°, respectively, corresponding to the sub-transus temperature range for each composition.

Interfacial shear strength results were analyzed with the aid of a specially-developed computer program that produced a link strength model virtual fiber based on experimentally determined fiber flow population data and subjected it to simulated tensile tests [4, 5].

TITANIUM MATRIX FRAGMENTATION SPECIMEN FABRICATION

Microcomposite specimens were fabricated with two, or three widely-separated fibers to minimize fiber-fiber interactions. Specimen fabrication was designed to accurately reflect the conditions experienced by high volume fraction composites.

Single fiber fragmentation specimens were fabricated by vacuum hot pressing SiC fibers between sheets or foils of matrix sandwiched between boron nitride parting agent-coated steel plates within a hot pressing die. In all cases, the rolling direction of the foil or sheet was parallel to the fiber axis. Composites produced with preform sheets were prepared with grooves machined in the sheets to retain, align, and protect the fibers during the heat up-phase [6]. The fibers at the bottom of these grooves were not subjected to asperity contact pressures during the early stages of hot pressing, but were only loaded after the matrix reached elevated temperatures and began to flow.

Foil-fiber-foil multifiber microcomposite preforms were prepared in the following manner. To achieve accurate fiber alignment and spacing, fibers were first laid into grooves machined into a metal sheet to serve as an alignment template. The fibers were tacked in place in the alignment template with a very small amount of dilute fugitive binder. The template with fibers was then inverted and placed on the lower foil preform. The fibers were secured to the preform foil with fugitive binder. The template was then lifted free while holding the fibers in place on the foil. In this manner, fibers can be rapidly and accurately set in place. Spacing strips were included in foil-fiber-foil specimens to prevent damage to the fibers due to the potentially high contact pressures caused by the very low number of fibers compared with high volume fraction composites.

To conserve on the limited supply of Ti-22Al-23Nb foil available, foils were pressed between 0.4mm thick sheets of Ti-6Al-4V. This results in the "hybrid" composite microstructure shown in Fig. 2. This compromise may introduce some complications in the interpretation of the clamping forces exerted on the fiber by the matrix during fragmentation testing. These complications are under investigation.

Both fabrication methods were designed to produce microcomposites under conditions that accurately reflect the processing of actual components, while accommodating the differences necessitated by the very low fiber volume fractions (<1.0%). Tensile coupons were prepared by electrical discharge machining (EDM) of the hot-pressed composite plates. Reference fibers placed at the ends of the specimen (Fig. 1) were used to determine fiber alignment for EDM machining, and were used for metallographic specimens. Specimens were polished to remove EDM-damaged material and the boron nitride release layer, which can produce acoustic emissions.

Figure 1. Fabrication method for foil-fiber-foil microcomposite specimens.

Figure 2. Optical micrograph of SCS-6 fiber in Ti-22Al-23Nb foil clad in Ti-6Al-4V sheet.

FIBER PRESTRAIN CONTROL AND MEASUREMENT

The relationship between coupon strain and fiber strain is of vital importance in in-situ fiber strength (ISFS) testing, since the coupon strain is the controlled variable while the fiber strain at failure is the variable of interest. The difference between the two in the early stages of the fragmentation process when ISFS data is acquired, is equal to the residual strain in the fiber, developed during processing and cooling [4].

Due to the very low fiber volume fraction, approximately 0.2%, and the very high aspect ratios of the fibers, approximately 800/1, it was found that the fibers were axially strained by the sheets of matrix material as they flowed to completely fill the die cavity. This axial extension resulted in fracture of the weakened SCS-0 fibers, leading to variable residual prestrains upon cooling and development of CTE mismatch strains. Fibers that did not fracture were also left with varying residual strain, due to small variations in the fit between the preform plates and the die cavity, which changed the extent of axial matrix flow during consolidation.

This difficulty was resolved by pressing shorter fibers, 40 mm in length, within a 120 mm specimen so that the end regions of the preform plates provided frictional constraint to the flow of the mid-regions, minimizing axial fiber extension, and leaving a consistent residual strain arising primarily from the CTE mismatch.

Residual strain reference fibers the same length as the test fibers and situated directly between the gage sections of the tensile coupons were therefore incorporated into the specimens as shown in Fig. 1. Following EDM machining, the portions removed from between the gage sections which contained the reference fibers, were diamond polished at the ends to a 45° angle and etched briefly with Kroll's reagent to expose the fiber ends and allow microscope observation from the side. The fiber lengths were accurately measured, *in-situ*, with a measuring microscope, centered on the carbon or tungsten cores of the fibers at each end. Fibers were then removed from the matrix by

grinding away most of the matrix then digesting away the remainder with Kroll's reagent. The fiber lengths were again measured, and directly compared with the original lengths to determine residual strain. In this manner the residual fiber strains were both controlled, and accurately measured. The 40 mm fibers were found to be left at a consistent level of prestrain, in the Ti-6Al-4V, 1.27 mm thick sheet based composites, approximately equal to $0.4\% \pm 0.1\%$. Scatter in the prestrain measurements obtained by this technique was as low as 0.0028% strain.

Residual fiber strains were found to be significantly higher for the microcomposites fabricated with .076 mm thick Ti-22Al-23Nb foil or thin sheet than for comparable composites fabricated with thicker (1.27mm) Ti-6Al-4V sheets, on the order of 0.8% compared with 0.4%, respectively. The difference is thought to be attributable to the difference in the sheet or foil thickness, and not to differences in CTE (coefficient of thermal expansivity) or other matrix properties. The high CTE of the steel press plates ($12 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$) [7] apparently imposed higher thermal contraction strains on these thinner sheets which in turn, placed the fibers under very high compression loads.

Additional work is underway which implies that SiC reinforced titanium matrix microcomposites may be fabricated with well-controlled fiber prestrain ranging from approximately -1.0% to 0.0%.

ACOUSTIC EMISSION DATA ACQUISITION

Acoustic emission (AE) data were acquired by a Locan AT acoustic emission acquisition system, synchronized to the crosshead motion of the Instron tensile testing apparatus. Previous work has established a one-to-one correlation between high amplitude AE (generally > 90 dB) and fiber breaks, provided that the strain rate is low enough, and fibers are widely separated enough so that nearly simultaneous breaks are rare or nonexistent. Transducers were broad-band type and were affixed directly to the coupon by elastomer bands with silicone grease as a coupling agent. Time-of-flight data were acquired to isolate events occurring within the gage section from grip and machine noise. Accurate position detection was not attempted, since that information is not required for the analysis.

IN SITU FIBER STRENGTH TESTING

In-situ fiber strength testing is a technique related to the single fiber fragmentation test [8,9] which is commonly used for the characterisation of interfacial shear properties and failure modes for fiber-reinforced composites with high failure strain matrices. Coupons containing one or more widely separated fibers are prepared in a manner that accurately represents the fabrication of actual composite components. The initial strain offset between the fiber and matrix must be determined and the fiber modulus must also be known. The coupons were then loaded in axial tension while fiber fragmentation was monitored by acoustic emissions as a function of coupon strain. The fiber strain at each failure was then calculated by subtracting the residual strain offset between the fiber and coupon.

The breaks that were detected were then used to calculate the number of flaws with a given failure strain, per unit length of fiber. The flaw population data were used to generate a link-strength computer model "virtual fiber", and these virtual fibers were tensile tested within the computer to generate length/strength data that are in the same form as those obtained by conventional tensile testing, so that they can be directly compared with those results, and subjected to the same types of statistical analyses, i. e. fitted to Weibull distributions.

Fracture morphologies in titanium matrix fragmentation specimens may be simple single fractures, or, more commonly complex [6]. Shock energy from adjacent breaks appears to cause the crushing associated with the complex fracture morphology.

INTERFACIAL SHEAR STRENGTH AND FRICTION COEFFICIENTS

Interfacial shear strengths were evaluated from the single fiber fragmentation tests by using the measured values of *in-situ* fiber strength, determined from the same tests. In this manner, any changes in fiber strength as a result of processing are included in the analysis. A simple Kelly and Tyson model [10] of interfacial shear strength was used, with the fiber strength at the critical length determined from a log/linear plot of strength vs *in-situ* fiber strength used.

Interfacial friction coefficients were determined by making the assumption that the mechanical strength of the interface is sufficiently low that the shear traction transfer is dominated by friction due to the large radial clamping forces exerted by the matrix. As discussed in a previous communication, [4] this clamping force is equal to the flow strength of the matrix material because of the Poisson's ratio mismatch between the plastically deforming matrix and the elastic fiber.

Although it is ambiguous to report both an "interfacial shear strength" and an "interfacial friction coefficient" these may be understood as alternate interpretations and representations of the same data. The "interfacial strength" is always a combination of mechanical interlocking, chemical bonding, and physical adhesion which cannot be deconvoluted by known means. In the case of titanium matrix composites, the very low strengths associated with the carbon protective layers on fibers combined with the very high clamping forces exerted by the matrix give an interface that is dominated by frictional effects. In the case of polymer matrix composites, particular fiber glass composites which employ silane coupling agents, the reverse situation is true, with chemical bonding playing the primary role and friction having a secondary or negligible effect [10].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Matrix Microstructure and Interface Reaction

Fig. 3 shows an SCS-6 fiber surrounded by a sheath of magnetron sputter coated Ti-22Al-23Nb, itself surrounded by Ti-6Al-4V. The extent of reaction is much less than that experienced by the SCS-6 directly in the Ti-6Al-4V matrix. An SCS-6 fiber hot pressed between Ti-22Al-23Nb sheets which were themselves between Ti-6Al-4V sheets, etched in Kroll's reagent is shown in Fig. 2. The fiber coatings in these early composites were damaged and consolidation was incomplete.

Figure 3. SCS-6 magnetron sputter coated with Ti-22Al-23Nb and clad in hot pressed Ti-6Al-4V.

MATRIX AND INTERFACE MICROSTRUCTURE

The Ti-22Al-23Nb matrix surrounding the fiber is made up of a fine scale microstructure. As observed in the optical micrograph (Fig. 2), the lightly etched equiaxed grains measuring a few mm in size are the alpha-2 phase regions which are distributed in a continuous matrix of (O+B2) two-phase structure. The two-phase microstructure is composed of very fine laths which can be resolved in an SEM at higher magnifications. The volume fraction of the various phases as well as the thickness of the fiber/matrix reaction zone in this microcomposite appeared to be similar to those reported previously for the Ti-22Al-23Nb/SCS-6 composite [1].

The region where the Ti-22Al-23Nb sheets were bonded to the Ti-6Al-4V sheets shows a transition from a fine beta-stabilized microstructure to a somewhat coarser equiaxed (a+b) structure. The Ti-6Al-4V part adjacent to the bond line consists of a coarse lamellar (a+b) structure containing a higher amount of beta-stabilizer.

The extent of the reaction at the fiber/matrix interface, seen in Figs. 2, 3, and 4, was found to be significantly less for SCS fibers in Ti-22Al-23Nb than in Ti-6Al-4V [11]. However, the first foil-fiber-foil specimens were found to have sustained damage to the carbon or SiC/carbon interface coating during consolidation, (Fig. 2), and to be incompletely consolidated. Similar damage occurred to the A3C fibers, as shown in Fig 4.

To improve consolidation, the area of the foil spacer strips was reduced in subsequent runs, based on the observation that the spacer strips were heavily indenting the steel press plates and not flowing laterally as much as desired. To reduce damage to the fiber coatings, a longer soak period was used before the load was applied during the hot press cycle. Fig. 5 shows a composite fabricated with these changed parameters. The fiber coating is intact, except for small amounts of debris which appear to have been swept along its surface and deposited at the foil-fiber-foil junction. Consolidation was nearly complete. Additional refinements are expected to produce fully dense composites with undamaged coatings.

Figure 4. A3C fiber in Ti-22Al-23Nb foil specimen. Incomplete consolidation and interface coating damage can be seen at the 0° and 180° positions.

Figure 5. SCS-6 fiber in Ti-22Al-23Nb foil composite with intact fiber coatings.

INTERFACIAL SHEAR STRENGTHS AND IN-SITU FIBER STRENGTHS

Table 1 lists the in-situ fiber strengths, critical lengths, interfacial shear strengths, and interfacial friction coefficients for the various fiber/matrix/processing combinations.

Table 1. In-situ and ex-situ fiber strengths, fragment lengths, and interfacial shear strengths and friction coefficients for SiC fibers in titanium matrices.

Fiber/Matrix	In Situ Fiber Strength @ 25 mm (GPa)	Ex Situ Fiber Strength @ 25 mm (GPa) ⁴	Fragment Length (Lc) (mm)	Interfacial Shear Strength (MPa)	Interfacial Friction Coefficient
SCS-6/Ti-6Al-4V	3.4	3.9	0.46	738	0.79
Ultra SCS/Ti-6Al-4V	5.5	5.4	1.13	489	0.54
SCS-6/Ti-22-23 Foil	1.5		1.08	609	0.68
SCS-6/Ti-22-23 Sheet	2.4		0.98	686	0.66
A1C/Ti-6Al-4V	2.5		0.74	489	0.54
A3C/Ti-6Al-4V	3.9		1.33	255	0.28
SCS-6/MSC Ti-22-23			1.11	295	0.33

All specimens were tested at room temperature. The in-situ fiber strengths for SCS-6 and Ultra SCS fibers in Ti-6Al-4V matrices are in agreement with those obtained in conventional ex-situ tests after removal from the matrix by digestion [13]. Additional studies are planned to establish this correlation more closely. In situ fiber strengths for the initial foil-fiber-foil specimens showed considerable degradation of the fiber properties, probably as a result of the interface damage during consolidation, as discussed in the section on interface microstructure.

Interfacial shear strengths of SCS-6 fibers in Ti-6Al-4V and in foil and sheet Ti-22Al-23Nb were approximately the same. This is as expected, for the case in which consolidation conditions were not severe enough to penetrate the carbon coating layers. The interface properties were therefore constant and a function of the interface between the carbon layers and the silicon carbide, independent of the matrix.

Ultra SCS fibers were found to have significantly higher strength than SCS-6 fibers or A1C or A3C fibers. Interfacial friction coefficients were slightly lower than SCS-6, but additional data will be required to confirm this, since only a small amount of Ultra SCS fiber was available for testing. Magnetron sputter coated SCS-6 fibers in Ti-22Al-23Nb were tested, but high oxygen contents in these early samples makes interpretation of these data premature.

CONCLUSIONS

In situ fiber strengths were found to be significantly degraded in the initial specimens included in this study due to interface damage incurred during processing. Interfacial shear strengths and friction coefficients for SCS-6 fibers in the Ti-22Al-23Nb orthorhombic matrix appear to be the same as those in the conventional Ti-6Al-4V matrix, based on these preliminary data. Interfacial reactions were less severe in Ti-22Al-23Nb than in Ti-6Al-4V. Ultra SCS fibers showed significantly higher in-situ fiber strengths than other fibers tested. Methods have been developed for fabricating foil-fiber-foil microcomposites from orthorhombic matrices.

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